

Negative impacts of lipophilic toxins on zebrafish development, immune system, and tissue regeneration

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Abstract

The increase in distribution and frequency of Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) worldwide are cause of social and environmental concern globally. In southern Chile, HAB episodes have caused great losses due to high fish mortalities in salmonid farms and native fauna, affecting biodiversity, local economies, and threatening food safety. The most damaging episodes of HABs in this region of the Pacific Ocean are associated to phytoplankton species producers of paralytic shellfish poison (PSP), but episodes caused by producers of Diarrhetic Shellfish Poison (DSP) and other emergent lipophilic biotoxins have been increasingly detected. Sub-lethal toxic effects on mammals and the mechanisms of action described to date for DSP are diverse, although their impact on fish have been neglected. Using zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) as a model, we tested the effects of four lipophilic biotoxins: Okadaic acid, Dinophysis toxin-1, Dinophysis toxin-2, and Yessotoxin-1. We assessed the effects of sub-lethal concentrations on swim bladder inflation, touch response and locomotor activity on larvae, and the results suggest teratogenic impacts and/or neurotoxicity. Also, using fish expressing fluorescent proteins in a specific cell type and whole-mount staining, we detected changes in the distribution pattern of neutrophils and the amount of Goblet cells, suggesting an activation of the immune response of larvae. Finally, taking advantage of the zebrafish regenerative capacity, we used a tail-fin amputation protocol and detected a negative impact on tissue regeneration. These effects all together can have complex implications for environmental safety, biodiversity conservation and the salmon industry, since small amounts of toxins can probably increase susceptibility to other threats for fish, such as environmental pathogens.

Keywords: Diarrhetic shellfish toxin, lipophilic toxins, zebrafish, bioassays, toxicity

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Introduction

Aquaculture industry in Chile is one of the main economic activities, and is specially concentrated in the southern macrozone, where the main products are salmonid fishes and mussels. Pacific austral southern macrozone has constant Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) events, especially on summer, when toxic blooms produce frequently high mortalities in salmon farms. The salmon industry is usually pointed out as responsible for diverse socio-environmental problems in Chile due to water and oceanic floor pollution caused by the excessive use of antibiotics to treat and prevent pathogens and parasites attacks on salmon (Cabello, 2006), the waste from food and metabolism, fish escape effecting ecosystems, and the controversial relationship between aquaculture farms and the increasing occurrence of HABs (Quiñones *et al.*, 2019).

Fishes in salmon farms are submitted to very stressful conditions. High population density and poor water quality, which makes them very susceptible to diverse environmental hazards and pathogens. Considering this, the presence of microalgae producing cytotoxic venoms even in relatively low concentrations, could contribute to worsening the sanitary situation on salmon farms, by producing damage to the skin, affecting the immune system, and/or by reducing wound healing process. Therefore, we wanted to know if marine biotoxins present in Chilean coast can affect the immune response and the regenerative capacity of fishes, and if they can be considered as a risk factor for the transmission of infectious diseases in fish that are related to skin wounds.

To assess this, we studied the impact of four lipophilic biotoxins in zebrafish larvae as a teleost model, exposing them to three toxins from the Okadaic acid group: Okadaic Acid (OA), Dinophysis toxin-1 (DTX-1), Dinophysis toxin-2 (DTX-2), and to Yessotoxin-1 (YTX-1). OA and its derivatives DTX-1 and DTX-2 cause gastrointestinal illness in humans, but in animal models has also been related with cytotoxicity, genotoxicity, neurotoxicity and tumor promotion. While cytotoxic potential on diverse levels (ribotoxic, apoptotic, genotoxic) has also been reported for Yessotoxins (Korsnes and Korsnes., 2017), while at least one report reveals its possible neurotoxic effects (Pérez-Gómez, 2006).

Different studies remark the numerous advantages of using the zebrafish model (*Danio rerio*) for assessing the impacts of marine biotoxins on fishes (Berry *et al.*, 2007). Also, multiple genetic and molecular tools as transgenic reporter lines, vital cell dyes, antibodies, and whole-mount stain techniques are available.

Material and Methods

Toxins and exposure solutions

Certified Reference Material (CRM) from the National Research Council Canada was used. Okadaic Acid (CRM-OA-d), Dinophysistoxin-1 (CRM-DTX1-c), Dinophysistoxin-2 (CRM-DTX2-b), and Yessotoxin (CRM-YTX-c) certified solutions in methanol, were diluted in E3 culture medium (5 mM NaCl, 0.17 mM KCl, 0.33 mM CaCl₂, 0.33 mM MgSO₄, buffered to pH 7.0). Additionally, a solution of methanol

equivalent to concentration in the lowest toxin dilution, was used as solvent control, and a negative control group incubated in E3 medium.

Exposure and fishes

Fifteen zebrafish embryos of 24 to 72 h post fertilization (hpf) were exposed to two concentrations of each toxin on 96-well plates in groups of three embryos with a final volume of 50 μ L (De la Paz *et al.*, 2020) unless otherwise stated, at 26 °C with a daily 14 h light /10 h dark cycle. TAB5 wild type strain was used for general toxic response monitoring, and fin regeneration experiments. Transgenic line Tg(BACmpo:gfp) expressing GFP in the innate immune system neutrophil cells (Renshaw *et al.*, 2006) was used for neutrophil and Goblet cells quantification.

Toxic response monitoring

Survival, edemas and the swim bladder air filling were monitored daily. After 24 h of exposure, locomotor activity was recorded for six hours with three hours period of light and dark, using an automated movement recorder system (WMicrotracker ONE, Phylumtech S.A.), later in the two following days the touch response index was evaluated similarly as previously described (Lefebvre *et al.*, 2004). Shortly, the caudal region was touched using a fine forceps, and reaction scored as following: (3) normal escape reaction, two body length is traveled away from the stimulus, at first touch; (2) delayed response, more than one touch is required for the scape response, (1) reduced response, the animal can't travel the normal distance away from the stimulus, but present a reaction; (0) the animal is totally paralyzed and do not react to the stimulus.

Neutrophil cells quantification

Transgenic Tg(BACmpo:gfp) 24 hpf embryos were exposed for 48 hours, then anesthetized with MS-222, and the number of GFP marked cells were quantified in different regions of the body using a Olympus IX81 epifluorescence microscope.

Goblet cell quantification

After neutrophil quantification, live embryos were incubated again for an additional 30 h (total exposure time 78 h), then transferred to PFA 4% and stained with Alcian Blue 8X (Sigma-Aldrich). Goblet cells in the head and trunk region, were quantified.

Caudal fin regeneration assay

The caudal fin of larvae was amputated, and regeneration area measured as previously described (Morales and Allende, 2019). One hour after amputation groups of six 4 dpf larvae were exposed to E3 medium, 0.5% methanol, AO, DTX-2 and YTX. Three days post amputation the caudal fin area was measured from images captured in an Olympus MVX10 stereomicroscope and analyzed using the ImageJ free software.

Statistical Analysis

For all statistical analysis the Graphpad Prism 9 for macOS software was used. Cell quantification, touch response and caudal fin regeneration data were analyzed with Kruskal Wallis test & Dunn's multiple comparison ($p < 0.05$). For locomotor activity and developmental defects Mann-Whitney test with a multiple comparison with Holm-Sidak method ($p < 0.05$) was used.

Results and Discussion

Neuro-motor response

Locomotor activity in zebrafish larvae raised in a 14 h light/10 h dark photoperiod, decrease its locomotor activity in prolonged dark periods of several hours. When 4 dpf larvae exposed to OA, DTX-1 and YTX for 24 h, were exposed to light changing conditions, the response in the beginning of a dark period was an increase of locomotor activity in toxin treated larvae respect to the control groups in this condition, but statistical analysis revealed a significant only for YTX, that also induce a reduction of touch response in larvae after three days of exposure (data not shown). These results suggests that these lipophilic toxins could have some impact on neuro-motor system in zebrafish larvae.

Survival and acute toxicity

None of the toxins was lethal or induced edemas, but results revealed that exposure to methanol and YTX by immersion can inhibit normal development of the swim bladder (Fig. 1), the flotation organ of larvae that allows buoyancy control, so it is possible that the impact of YTX to fishes on natural environment could affect normal swimming, feeding, and escape capacity on fish larval stages. Therefore, YTX may have an indirect negative impact on fish populations by reduce viability of early stages of fish, and by impeding essential biological functions.

Fig. 1. Yessotoxin and methanol affects development of zebrafish swim bladder. (A) normal zebrafish larva. (B) Treated larva with not inflated swim bladder (arrows). (C) Average and SD of filled swim bladder. (**p < 0.01).

Immune cells responses

The first normal response of fishes exposed to noxious chemical or physical agents is the production of skin mucus secreted mainly by epidermal Goblet Cells (Shepard, 1993). Fish skin mucus contains diverse defensive components including glycoproteins, glycosaminoglycans, and several antimicrobial proteins, acting as a first defensive barrier of the innate immune system (Dash *et al.*, 2018

To resolve if lipophilic biotoxins can affect the defensive barrier of skin and immune system, we assessed the number of skin Goblet cells in the head and trunk of exposed zebrafish larvae. Results shows that even when the solvent control induce a reduction in the number of stained mucus cells, the number is significantly lower when exposed to OA, DTX-1 and DTX-2 (Fig. 2). This shows that these biotoxins induces a response of the mucus producing cells in zebrafish larvae.

Fig. 2. OA and its derivatives impact skin Goblet cells abundance. Zebrafish larvae exposed to lipophilic toxins present a reduced number of mucus cells (blue dots on left) on the skin of trunk. (* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$). N 12-13 individuals.

Fig. 3. Lipophilic marine biotoxins induce neutrophil migration to yolk region. Leukocytes in the yolk sac area (yellow oval) of larvae exposed was quantified *in vivo*. Mean and SD (* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$).

If defensive barriers of mucus and skin are breached, recruitment of neutrophil cells is the first cellular response, and their early activity is necessary not only for pathogen elimination or entry prevention, but also for the subsequent wound regeneration process (Philipson and Kubes, 2019).

Using a transgenic zebrafish strain that expresses the Green Fluorescent Protein (GFP) in neutrophils, we detected that these inflammatory cells migrate specifically to the yolk region of the embryo after being exposed for 48 hours to OA, DTX-1, and YTX (Fig. 3), suggesting a specific cell migration or recruitment to the yolk region that can account for an activation of the innate immune system of the larvae challenged with these biotoxins. Since the relationship between these biotoxins and the fish immune system is practically unknown, the kinetic response for this (and other) cell types should be further studied to make conclusions.

Caudal fin regeneration on zebrafish larvae
To assess possible impacts of YTX and OA and its derivatives on fish tissue regeneration, we executed a caudal fin amputation protocol in the larvae. Results showed that the regeneration process when exposed YTX is affected (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Yessotoxin affects caudal fin regeneration on zebrafish larvae. Mean and SD for regenerated caudal fin area. Dotted line shows amputation site (** $p < 0.01$).

Our results show that these four lipophilic biotoxins on water can induce a quantifiable response on at least two innate immune cell types: mucus producing Goblet cells (AO,

DTX-1 and DTX-2), and inflammatory neutrophils (AO, DTX-1 and YTX), and can also affect tissue regenerative capacity on zebrafish larvae (YTX).

The possible relationship between these toxins and the innate immune response and regenerative capacity in fishes is not understood to date. This is the first report on this topic, and therefore, more studies are needed to resolve if lipophilic biotoxins can be a risk factor for the transmission of infectious diseases associated to skin wounds in fishes, by impairing mucus physical barrier, cellular innate immune response and/or hindering wound healing and tissue regeneration. More studies are needed to unravel the relationship between the occurrence of HABs, their impacts on general animal health, and on early fish stages. Considering the global warning scenario and the environmental and socio-economic consequences of HABs events in Chile, we consider this a critical matter in zones with high aquaculture activity.

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References

- Berry, J. P., Gantar M., Gibbs P. D., Schmale M. C. (2007). *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. C Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 145, 61-72.
- Cabello, F. C. (2006). *Environm. Microbiol.* 8, 1137-1144.
- Dash, S., Das, S. K., Samal, J., Thatoi, H. N. (2018). *Iran. J. Vet. Res.* 19, 72-81.

De la Paz, J. F., Anguita-Salinas, C., Díaz-Celis, C., Chávez, F. P., Allende, M. L. (2020). *Biomolecules* 10, 1274.

Korsnes, M. S. and Korsnes, R. (2017). *Front. Cell. Dev. Biol. Mar.* 31, 5-30.

Lefebvre, K. A., Trainer, V. L., Scholz, N. L. (2004). *Aquat. Toxicol.* 66, 159-170.

Morales, R. A. and Allende, M. L. (2019). *Front. Immunol.* 10, 253.

Pérez-Gómez A., Ferrero-Gutierrez A., Novelli A., Franco J. M., *et al.*, (2006). *Toxicol. Sci.* 90, 168-77.

Renshaw, S. A., Loynes, C. A., Trushell, D. M., Elworthy, S., *et al.*, (2006). *Blood* 108, 3976-3978.

Shepard, K. L. (1993). *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* 11, 403-417.

Quiñones, R. A., Fuentes, M., Montes, R. M., Soto, D., León-Muñoz, J. (2019). *Rev. Aquacult.* 11, 375-402.

